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Within Speech Therapy and Linguistics

[*Studia logopedyczno-lingwistyczne. Księga Jubileuszowa z okazji 70-lecia urodzin profesora Edwarda Łuczyńskiego*, ed. S. Milewski, K. Kaczorowska-Bray, B. Kamińska, wyd. Harmonia: Gdańsk 2017, pp. 500.]

Studia logopedyczno-lingwistyczne (*Studies on Speech Therapy and Linguistics*) is an anthology prepared by eminent members of the research community in Gdańsk – Stanisław Milewski, Katarzyna Kaczorowska-Bray and Barbara Kamińska. The publication clearly shows the current state of speech therapy. Having gained its due reputation as an area of research, it now integrates not only its subdisciplines (such as neurological speech therapy, speech therapy for the hard of hearing, as well as artistic, corrective and educational speech therapy) but also other studies, such as linguistics. The fact that the publication offers such an image of speech therapy is certainly a significant advantage.

The anthology is dedicated to Professor Edward Łuczyński to mark the occasion of his 70th birthday. Professor Łuczyński is a renowned expert among speech therapists and linguists, an outstanding theoretician of the culture of the Polish language, and a practitioner who is valued for his innovative approach to diagnosis and treatment in speech therapy. The outline of his life and work is presented both in the introduction to the anthology, as well as in *O sobie* (*About myself*), a text written by the Professor himself in which he sets forth his academic biography, marked first by a fascination with linguistics, later with speech therapy. Professor

Łuczyński's work has had a lasting effect and influence on both of these areas of study.

This extensive publication is divided into two parts, with *Studia logopedyczne* (*Speech Therapy Studies*) at 17 texts and *Rozprawy językoznawcze* (*Papers on linguistics*) at 7 texts, in which speech therapists and linguists present concepts, make hypotheses, discuss stimulation techniques as well as helpful diagnostic and research tools, specify research problems, describe case studies, and suggest therapy methods. The authors altogether managed to account for a considerable variety of cases (muteness, aphasia, bilingualism, mental disabilities, ADHD etc.), which gives not only a reliable picture of research in those areas but also many useful guidelines for readers who are mostly interested in the practical aspects of speech therapists' work. This is because the anthology not only features texts that focus strictly on the theoretical issues of the two disciplines but also offers studies that are a result of many years of experience gained by representatives of the most important Polish research and therapy centres (in Lublin, Gdańsk, Kraków, Katowice, Bydgoszcz and Warszawa).

Papers on linguistics complement the studies on speech therapy, and even though more articles deal with speech therapy throughout this anthology, it is ultimately the part concerning linguistics that shows the human element in using a language, touching upon such issues as grammatical and lexical structures used by young Polish speakers, word formation, vocabulary analyses, as well as psycholinguistics and cognitive linguistics. Thanks to this, the anthology will not only capture the interest of speech therapists but also attract the attention of linguists, psychologists, pedagogues and the parents who wish to be supportive partners for therapists.

Articles that address the problems of multilingualism and multiculturalism in this anthology deserve special attention in particular, as the changes in demographics, culture and the economy which have taken place in recent years put many parents in a position where they have to raise their children bilingually. Given these circumstances, in *Metoda Krakowska wobec zaburzeń rozwoju dzieci. Z perspektywy fenomenologii, neurobiologii i językoznawstwa* (*The Cracow Method and Developmental Disorders in Children. From the Phenomenological, Neurobiological and Linguistic Point of View*), Jagoda Cieszyńska highlights the need to stimulate the development of Polish children who live abroad. Furthermore, Cieszyńska describes specific stimulation techniques and provides extensive guidance on how to implement them, which is invaluable for specialists and parents who deal

with bilingualism. In her suggestions, she refers to the latest findings on the neurobiological mechanisms governing the organisation of language functions in the brain; these, in turn, are the basis for stimulation techniques described in her paper. Interestingly, Cieszyńska also suggests using similar techniques for monolingual children with neurodevelopmental disorders.

Zbigniew Tarkowski and Dorota Wiewióra deal with a similar topic in *Bilingwizm a rozwój mowy dziecka (Bilingualism and Speech Development in Children)*. This article, divided into a theoretical introduction and a part focused on research, is a clear and comprehensive discussion of the subject, which the authors have examined in great depth. What is the most interesting in this article, however, is the part that deals with innovative research. The authors undertake to assess the speech of bilingual children. The insufficient population of the subjects does not allow them to draw any clear conclusions, but this is to no detriment of the study's significance, as it may serve as the basis for future research in this respect. It is worth noting that Tarkowski's and Wiewióra's study is the first of such kind in Poland. The article also features an interesting suggestion to establish bilingual speech therapy as a separate degree at faculties of language, which, considering the growing tendency for cultures to mix and people to emigrate, seems to be fully justified.

Most speech therapists have encountered people with intellectual disabilities in their work, which is why Katarzyna Kaczorowska-Bray's study, *Zaburzenia mowy u dzieci z niepełnosprawnością intelektualną – trudności badawcze (Speech Disorders in Children with Intellectual Disabilities – Obstacles in Research)* merits to be studied attentively, from the point of view of both speech therapy and linguistics. The author discusses one of the fundamental problems people with intellectual disabilities have to face – the constraints in language communication. Well aware of the inconsistencies in how this group's ability to communicate is described, Kaczorowska-Bray emphasises that it is necessary to conduct empirical research on language impairments and speech pathology in people with intellectual disabilities. This would allow either for confirming or dismissing specific linguistic phenomena observable in their utterances.

Halina Waszczuk's paper, a report on the implementation of an original *Rodzinna Terapia Jąkania (Family Stuttering Therapy)* programme, is devoted to key aspects of stuttering therapy. In the paper, Waszczuk rightly points to the multifaceted nature of the disorder, and presents stuttering systemically, discussing its psychological, social and biological foundations one by one, and exposing the connections between them. Waszczuk also

refers to her own experience in conducting Parent-Child Interaction Therapy, and puts great emphasis on the need to take comprehensive therapeutic measures and approach stuttering from the point of view of many professions, such as speech therapists, psychologists and doctors.

Yet another interesting article, Barbara Kamińska's *Język w radiu jako przedmiot zainteresowań logopedii medialnej* (*The Language of Radio as a Point of Interest for Media Speech Therapy*) concerns the functioning of the voice in the specific voice tasks performed and in the profession of a radio announcer. Kamińska describes the radio announcers' voice work as requiring special care with respect to words and sounds, and includes important information for media speech therapy in the introduction to her article, where she makes a skilful overview of selected studies on the language of radio. What is important is that Kamińska points to the deficit in descriptions of phonic realisations of radio utterances as well as to the need for further research on phenomena observable in radio journalists' speech, such as intonation changes, illogical phrasing, chaotic pauses and fast speech rate. Furthermore, the fact that the author considers the need for media speech therapists is valuable for radio audiences as well as for knowledge users and experts.

The anthology pertains to key problems and phenomena in modern-day speech therapy and linguistics. It conveniently combines theoretical and empirical studies, and encourages further attempts at popularising these areas of research, in terms of both didactic and cognitive considerations. The language used by the authors is accessible, and does not discourage readers from the texts themselves. What sets the anthology apart from other books is the multifaceted point of view from which speech therapy and linguistics are addressed, and the fact that the authors have indisputably intertwined the two disciplines. The structure of the book is clear and transparent, the theoretical and methodological elements are presented concisely and conveniently, while research demonstrated by many scholars in the anthology can serve as the basis for further scientific discussions.